

Multifaceted Design of Surface Passivator for Upgraded Charge Extraction in Perovskite Solar Cells

Mahdi Gassara, Samrana Kazim, Shahzada Ahmad**

BCMaterials, Basque Center for Materials, Applications, and Nanostructures, UPV/EHU
Science Park, 48940, Leioa, Spain

E-mail: shahzada.ahmad@bcmaterials.net

Materials Physics Center, CSIC-UPV/EHU, Paseo Manuel de Lardizabal 5, 20018, Donostia -
San Sebastian, Spain

E-mail: samrana.kazimk@ehu.eus

IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, Bilbao, 48009, Spain

The non-radiative recombination arising at the interfaces of perovskite solar cells poses a significant hurdle, impacting both the efficiency and stability of devices. Functionalized organic molecules can passivate the perovskite surface to suppress the defects and can also tune the microstructure to boost stability. This in turn promotes reliability and performance. Using a design protocol we synthesized and employed cyanoguanidine diiodide as a surface passivator for the fabrication of perovskite solar cells, and achieved boosted performance from 20.44% to 23.04%. This improvement stems from an improved fill factor reached up to 80.64%, together with the open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) measuring 1119 mV. The steady-state photoluminescence and microstructure of passivated perovskites display significant surface modification of the perovskite film which favorably impacts the charge carrier transfer at the interface of perovskite and Spiro-OMeTAD. Our findings suggest improved solar cell performance due to the synergistic effect of amino and cyano functional groups along with the iodide reservoir in the organic passivator.

Keywords: Perovskite, Passivation, Surface modification, defect density

1. Introduction

Thin film photovoltaic research witnessed a revolution with the arrival of perovskite solar cells (PSCs), showcasing a remarkable enhancement in power conversion efficiency (PCE). In a decade, PSCs have witnessed a substantial increase in performance, soaring from 3.8% to 26.5%.^[1-3] However, the PSCs have not yet demonstrated the required operational stability under accelerated aging tests due to defects present at the surface, which are aggravated by

operationality.^[4] Though a remarkable PCE has been attained and enhancements are being reported, the prospect of approaching 30%, exists as predicted theoretically.^[5-6] To attain the theoretical limits in performance, it is essential to control charge recombination and minimize various nonradiative recombination losses in both the bulk and interfaces.^[7] In this vein, the main contributors to non-radiative recombination losses in PSCs are deep-level defects, characterized by a thermal activation energy higher than $k_B T$.^[8,9]

The high-performance PSCs are typically fabricated from bulk (3D) perovskites, while, layered perovskites have shown higher stability.^[10] Arguably, improving the stability of 3D perovskites is paramount. By drawing inspiration from the stability-inducing properties of Lewis bases in layered perovskites, it can be a guiding force to induce stability in bulk perovskites. In this context, the utilization of organic molecules with long chains as passivator agents not only reduces ion migration from the perovskite to the hole transport material (HTM) but also serves as a barrier against the volatility of formamidinium (FA) and methylammonium (MA).^[11] So far, a range of organic materials, as passivators, have been employed in perovskite thin films to impede defect formation or decrease defect density by interacting molecularly with undercoordinated metal cations or halide anions.^[12-14] Surface passivation of the perovskite is particularly regarded as the most effective method to mitigate nonradiative recombination losses and, subsequently, to boost the photovoltage.^[15,16] Undercoordinated ions can be passivated through ionic or coordinate bonding by employing species with opposite charges, while vacancies can be filled by either ammonium cations or halide anions.^[17]

Currently, phenyl ethyl-ammonium iodide (PEAI) is the most exploited choice as a surface passivator for halide perovskite, allowing suppression of non-radiative recombination and surface defect reduction, to optimize performance.^[18] Moreover, PEAi provides surface passivation along with the ability to interact on $\{100\}$ and $\{111\}$ of the perovskite grain, this interaction is due to the different sizes of the passivation grains, making PEAi a preferred choice over other amine functionalization.^[19] In addition to surface passivation, addressing ion migration is imperative to enhance the longevity of PSCs. Studies have demonstrated that Ag^+ ions can migrate through the absorber layer similarly to halide ions. Although the diffusion barrier for Ag^+ is on par with that of highly mobile iodide ions, the defects caused by Ag^+ are relatively benign.^[20-22] To counteract potential degradation from silver ion migration, passivation techniques are being implemented to improve the stability of the perovskite by reducing defect densities and blocking ion migration pathways.

This work entails the designing of an organic halide salt for surface passivation of perovskites. We deduce the impact of typical passivating salts on PSCs stability and

performance and uncover the interactive role of the halide salt with an FA-rich perovskite with a single halide source ($\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{MA}_{0.05}\text{PbI}_3$). Three surface passivators, PEAI, imidazolium iodide (ImI), and cyanoguanidine diiodide (DYI) are selected to elucidate their impact on mitigating surface defects at the interface between the perovskite and the HTM. The $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ and $-\text{C}=\text{NH}$ functional groups present in DYI can interact with the uncoordinated Pb^{2+} in perovskite, and in turn will reduce the non-radiative recombination, while the iodide will serve as a reservoir for ions and will fill the vacancy stemmed from ion migration. The $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ and $-\text{C}=\text{NH}$ functional groups in DYI can donate the electron instantly and strong coordination effect with Pb^{2+} , arguably this will retard perovskite's tendency for oxidation.

The PSCs passivated with DYI achieved a PCE of 23.04%, because of an enhanced fill factor (FF) of 80.65% and an open-circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 1119 mV. In comparison, the control PSC yielded a V_{oc} of 1077 mV, and an FF of 75.84%, achieving an overall PCE of 20.44%. Moreover, the DYI passivated PSCs showed enhanced operational stability compared to the control when stored under dry air conditions. By employing an array of techniques, we uncover the impact of the passivator on the structural and optical properties of perovskite and noted that DYI passivation suppresses non-radiative recombination and enhances charge carrier mobility compared to PEAI and ImI.

2. Results and Discussion

Thin films of CsFAMAPbI_3 perovskite were prepared by a spin coating method and followed by spin-coating of the passivators molecules (DYI, PEAI, and ImI) from isopropanol solutions. In the diffraction pattern, peaks at $2\theta = 14.04^\circ, 19.87^\circ, 24.39^\circ, 28.20^\circ, 31.58^\circ, 34.71^\circ, 38.73^\circ, 40.30^\circ,$ and 42.82° matches with (100), (110), (111), (200), (210), (211), (220), and (300) planes of and are the characteristics peak of hybrid halide perovskite respectively. The peaks at $2\theta = 12.73^\circ$ correspond to the characteristics peak of PbI_2 . Slight shifts were noted in the diffraction patterns of PEAI- and DYI-passivated perovskites. The absence of the peaks ($2\theta < 10^\circ$) indicates that the passivating molecule did not form the layered perovskite structure, thus, it will not increase the quantum and dielectric confinement of the perovskite thin films. [23-24] Moreover the intensity of the PbI_2 peak ($2\theta = 12.7^\circ$) reduces and exhibited to be lowest for DYI and follows the trend, $\text{DIY} < \text{PEAI} < \text{ImI} < \text{control}$ (Figure S1), while the diffraction peak intensities of the (100) and (200) crystal planes in DYI passivated perovskite enhances and thus, improved crystallization and changed in the local environment of surface (Figure S1).

Figure 1. a) Schematic diagram of PSC and the organic passivator molecules, Electrostatic potential analysis of PEAi, ImI, and DYI, b) XRD pattern of perovskite films with different passivators, and c) the molecular structure of the organic passivator molecules (PEAI, ImI, and DYI) with corresponding electrostatic potentials (ESP) analyses calculated with Gaussian software.

To elucidate the chemical interaction between the perovskite and passivator molecules, we performed proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy ($^1\text{H-NMR}$) and to do this, the perovskite powder was scratched from the thin films (Figure S2). In the proton spectra, the signals of the amino group exhibited a downfield shift, attributed to the electrostatic interaction with the passivator molecule with perovskites, which stems from the increased electronegativity of the nitrogen atom.^[25-26]

To deduce further information about the molecular dipole moment of methyl pairs to NH-related molecules, we performed density functional theory (DFT) calculations to learn the electrostatic potential (ESP). In the ESP (Figure 1c), the electron-deficient region (positive region) is mainly distributed in the amine group and the electron-donating substituents on the benzene ring. Equally, the amine fraction of PEAi, the C–H of ImI, and the $-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ of DYI, in the acceptor moiety exhibits a high-density electronic cloud (negative region), which provides optimal conditions for coordination with insufficiently coordinated Pb^{2+} cations, while the nitrogen site is in contrast to the π -conjugated system. The effective coupling of intermolecular orbitals allows the transfer of electrons from the donor moiety to the acceptor moiety. This

effect can further enhance the interaction between ionic defects with insufficient coordination in perovskite crystals.^[27-28] UV-vis absorption spectra of passivated perovskite film (Figure 2) display similar absorption to the pristine perovskite. However, steady-state photoluminescence (PL) exhibits a varying emission intensity, as compared to the pristine perovskite. The emission intensity peak increases with PEAI and DYI, while with ImI the PL intensity decreases as compared to the pristine perovskite. This suggests the impacts of organic passivators on the optoelectronic properties of perovskite films. Specifically, PEAI and DYI modified perovskite exhibit higher PL intensity, indicating a reduction in non-radiative recombination losses and improved charge carrier dynamics. To elucidate the optimal concentration of DYI, we screened it from 1 – 5 mg/ml (Figure S3a). Expectedly, the thickness of the passivators has no bearing on the absorption of the perovskite, and the steady-state PL of perovskite/DYI displayed a similar emission peak at 800 nm but with a change in peak intensities can be observed. The optimal DYI passivation is noted to be at 2 mg/ml (Figure S3b), where it shows maximum PL intensity. Further, with the deposition of the hole transport layer (HTL) and following the configuration perovskite/DYI/Spiro, the PL intensities of the DYI passivated are quenched compared to the pristine perovskites, suggesting improved carrier separation and transport at the perovskite-HTL interface with DYI passivation, potentially reducing non-radiative recombination losses. PEAI and DYI, reduce the non-radiative recombination on the perovskite surface, while ImI alters the perovskite surface and induces defects at the perovskite/Spiro interface.

Figure 2. a) UV-vis absorption spectra, and b) steady-state PL of perovskite, and passivated perovskite thin-films (PEAI, ImI, DYI).

Figure 3. a) FTIR spectra of passivated perovskite thin film with PEAI, ImI, and DYI, b) N-H stretching region, c) C=N and C-N stretching region, and XPS spectra of d) Pb 4f, and e) I 3d of perovskite and DYI passivated perovskites thin films.

To understand the underlying passivation mechanisms on perovskite facets, it is essential to accurately identify and analyze the specific facets present on the surface of the perovskite thin film. The PEA^+ ions contain double bonds with delocalized π electrons in their benzene rings, while the ImI ions are composed of single bonds only, and DYI could interact with both $(-\text{NH}_3^+)_2$ terminals via hydrogen bonding. Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was performed, and transmission bands at 1100 and 900 cm^{-1} correspond to C–N stretching, and around $3450\text{--}3200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to N–H stretching, originating from the FA^+/MA^+ cation (Figure 3a). The signal detected at around 1712.2 cm^{-1} represents symmetric C=N stretching from FA^+ in the perovskite.^[29-30] The C-N stretching vibration peak shifts from 1352 to 1354 cm^{-1} with PEAI, and ImI, and to 1354.2 cm^{-1} for DYI, indicating the interaction with perovskite. Similarly, we noted the N-H stretching shifts from 3263 (pristine) to 3266 , 3264 , and 3269 cm^{-1} with PEAI, ImI, and DYI, respectively. This is attributed to the presence of hydrogen bonding between the iodide and the surface passivators.^[31]

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) data for Pb 4f and I 3d are derived from the overall survey spectra (Figure 3c and d). The occurrence of the characteristic peaks of Pb 4f_{5/2} and 4f_{7/2} of the pristine appears at 143.49 and 138.64 eV, respectively. After DYI passivation, the peaks have shifted to the lower binding energy with a value of 143.37 and 138.50 eV, respectively. Similar shifts were observed in the I 3d_{3/2} and I 3d_{5/2} from 630.95 and 619.44 eV to 630.73 and 619.27 eV, respectively, indicating that the binding capacity of the iodide and lead atoms on the perovskite surface has changed due to the interaction between the passivation layer and the PbI₂.^[32,35] Moreover, the existence of Pb⁰ in perovskite thin films can hinder the crystallization process, adding shallow defects and lowering the trap activation energy. This leads to deteriorated PCE and the stability of the perovskite film.^[36,38] The presence of the DYI layer alters the Pb chemical environment and hinders metallic Pb (Pb⁰) formation, (Figure 3c), the concentration of Pb⁰ decreases from 5.26% in the control film to 3.76%.

To evaluate the effectiveness of the developed passivator on the photovoltaic performance of PSCs, we fabricated planar n-i-p devices with the configuration FTO/SnO₂/perovskite/Spiro-OMeTAD/Ag. As anticipated, the PSCs with DYI passivation gave a superior performance as compared to the pristine, PEAI, and ImI passivation. The *J-V* curves are shown (Figure 4a) and it can be deduced that the passivators improve the device FF, while PEAI and DYI (81.47 and 80.65 respectively) delivered high FF, suggesting their suitability over ImI. The difference in PCE between PEAI and DYI is related to higher *V_{oc}* obtained by DYI (1119 mV) passivators. A compact and large perovskite grain formation is deduced, which will allow the homogeneous deposition of the subsequent Spiro-OMeTAD layer, leading to an effective hole separation and extraction with the DYI passivation. The external quantum efficiency (EQE) (Figure 4b) reaches a value of 81.8 % for the control PSC, and it shows increment with passivation, to 86.96, 87.32, and 89.18 % with PEAI, ImI, and DYI, respectively. The calculated values of integrated current (*J_{sc}*) from the EQE are 22.37, 22.44, 23.40, and 24.47 mA/cm² for control, PEAI, ImI, and DYI respectively. Figure 4c-f illustrates the statistical distribution of the PCE, *V_{oc}*, short-circuit current density (*J_{sc}*), and fill factor (FF). The forward and reverse *J-V* scans are also represented (Figure S4) to gaze anomalies in *J-V* measurements.

Figure 4. a) J - V characterization, and b) EQE spectra of the corresponding PSCs along with the integrated current (J_{sc}) obtained from the EQE for control, PEAI, ImI, and DYI respectively, and c-f) displays the statistical distribution of photovoltaic parameters for control, PEAI, ImI, and DYI passivated PSCs. Empty squares denote the mean value.

Surface topography was investigated (Figure 5), revealing that the perovskite microstructure is influenced by the passivating molecule and exhibits variations in grain distribution. The pristine perovskite (Figure 5a) and the ImI passivated present different grains and sizes, suggesting the interaction with the ImI allows the modification in the grain texture (Figure 5b), while uniform and compact grain with PEAI and DYI are noted.

Figure 5. Surface (top view) scanning electron microscopy image for a) pristine perovskite, b) perovskite with PEAI, c) perovskite with ImI, and d) perovskite with DYI passivation.

The use of a multifunctional additive with amino and cyano groups having lone pair electrons can interact effectively with the Pb–I and iodide, allowing the formation of compact and dense perovskite thin films having low trap density and improved carrier lifetime. The scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images on a large-scale bar (Figure S5) show that PEAI produces grains of variable sizes, with visible grain boundaries (Figure S5c). The DYI-passivated perovskite thin film (Figure 5d) shows a uniform grain size, to the reference and PEAI. The DYI also tends to crystallize in the grain's boundary, which allows for reducing the gaps by filling the grain boundaries and minimizing the defect density. The histogram of grain size (Figure S6) derived from (Fig. S5), suggests a large mean grain size for DYI passivated perovskites. The cross-section image of the fabricated PSC (Figure S7e), showed a perovskites thickness of 428 nm. The surface roughness is measured by scanning force microscopy (Figure S7), and the passivators impact the roughness of the perovskite films. Lower root mean square (RMS) values of 25.5 nm for the pristine to 24.19, 24.52, and 23.07 nm for PEAI, ImI, and DYI, respectively are measured, which suggests the role of DYI in forming a dense, compact, and uniform microstructure, stemming from the favorable crystallization with DYI, which in turn will be beneficial for the interfacial contact between the perovskite and the hole transport layer to facilitate effective hole extraction.

Figure 6. a) Nyquist plots of PSCs without and with DYI passivation measured at an applied voltage of 900 mV in the dark (raw and fitted data), b) charge transport resistance, and c) interfacial charge recombination resistance extracted from Nyquist plots under dark conditions.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was carried out in dark conditions to deduce the charge dynamics in the PSCs. The EIS data was fitted (Fig.6a) with an equivalent circuit comprising a series resistance (R_s), a charge transport resistance (R_{ctr}), and a recombination resistance (R_{rec}) at the interface between the perovskite and the hole transport layer. Additionally, two constant phase elements (Capacitors C1 and C2) were included in parallel to account for carrier diffusion in the perovskite and selective layers, to estimate the value of R_{ctr} and R_{rec} . For the charge transfer resistance (R_{ctr}), DYI passivation demonstrates a greater reduction in resistance from 512.3 to 280 Ω at higher applied voltages (0.9 V) compared to the control PSC (Figure 6b). This indicates that the passivation of deep-level defects in the perovskite bulk enhances charge transport at the interface between the perovskite and hole transport layer (Perovskite/HTL), with DYI providing further improvement.

Meanwhile, under the same bias conditions, PEAI and DYI passivation featured a higher R_{rec} than control PSCs for all the applied voltage up to 0.9 V (Figure 6c & S8). The DYI based device demonstrates a significant enhancement in recombination resistance (R_{rec}) at 0.9 V, rising from 383.3 to 585 Ω compared to the control device. This improvement is attributed to reduced charge annihilation at the interface and more efficient charge extraction, as depicted in (Figure 6c).

To deduce the leakage current and carrier recombination behaviors of PSCs with different passivation, dark $J-V$ measurements (Figure S9a) showed that the reverse current of PSCs treated with PEAI, ImI, and DYI are reduced by an order of magnitude compared to pristine PSCs. To estimate the defect state density, hole-only devices were fabricated with the structure ITO/PEDOT/perovskite(PEAI/ImI/DYI)/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au, and the space-charge limited current (SCLC) curves were analyzed (Figure S9b-d). The dark $J-V$ curves can be categorized

into three regions: ohmic, trap-filled limit (TFL), and Child region.^[32] The voltage at the intersection of the Ohmic and TFL regions (V_{TFL}) is directly proportional to the defect density (N_t), as follows ^[37]:

$$N_t = \frac{2\varepsilon_0\varepsilon_r V_{TFL}}{qL^2} \quad (1)$$

where ε_0 represents the vacuum permittivity ($\varepsilon_0 = 8.86 \times 10^{-14}$ F cm⁻¹), q is the elementary charge ($q = 1.60 \times 10^{-19}$ C), L indicates the thickness of the perovskite film ($L = 428$ nm) and ε_r is the relative permittivity of the perovskite. The density of the trap (N_t) is proportional to the V_{TFL} . The V_{TFL} of the control device decreases from 0.95 to 0.72, 0.86, and 0.82V with the passivation of PEAI, DYI, and ImI, respectively, suggesting, trap can be effectively filled by these organic passivators. (Figure S9 b-d).

The fabricated PSCs were stored in a desiccator without encapsulation, (Figure S10a). After 60 days of storage, the passivated PSCs maintained over 83% of their initial efficiencies, whereas the control PSC was only able to retain 77% of their initial efficiencies during the same period. After 120 days, the PCE showed significant differences among the samples stored in dry air. The control PSC exhibited a PCE of 0.41%, while PEAI, DYI, and ImI passivation showed PCE values of 14.69%, 15.43%, and 6.29%, respectively. The drastic reduction in PCE of the control PSC is attributed to the degradation of the perovskite layer and the deterioration of electrical properties. The passivated perovskites (PEAI and DYI) effectively acted as barriers, mitigating the diffusion, and subsequently retained their structural integrity and black color, (Figure S10b). ^[20-22,39] The perovskite film was tracked through UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy (Figure S11), showing a notable decrease in the absorption for the pristine and ImI passivated films, as compared to the PEAI and DYI passivated perovskites. While both PEAI and DYI show a slight decrease after 20 days of storage under ambient conditions. Measurements performed after 60 days of storage show a rapid decrease in the absorption for the reference and ImI passivated films (complete degradation and acquired yellow color), while the PEAI and DYI passivated perovskite thin films maintain their absorbance, indicating a barricading effect against moisture and oxygen. Both PEAI and DYI passivated films show a slower degradation and remain black.

3. Conclusion

In summary, We shed light on the role of passivation selection in enhancing perovskite solar cells by selecting three different passivators (PEAI, ImI, and DYI) in formamidinium-rich perovskites, revealing their impact on grain size, grain boundary defects, and microstructure.

The use of a multifaceted additive with amino and cyano groups interacts with the uncoordinated Pb^{2+} , allows the formation of compact and dense grains, and reduces the non-radiative recombination. This attests to the ability of cyanoguanidine diiodide to improve the charge carrier transfer between the perovskite and Spiro-OMeTAD. With the use of cyanoguanidine diiodide passivators, the fabricated solar cells showed improved structural stability and measured a power conversion efficiency of 23.04% as compared to the control device which measured 20.44%.

4. Experimental Section

Materials: The chemicals were purchased: lead iodide (99.99%) Tokyo Chemical Industry (TCI), cesium chloride (99.99%) (ThermoFisher), formamidinium iodide (99.99%), Methylammonium iodide and chloride (99.99%) (Greatcell Solar Materials). The organic salt passivators were purchased from Greatcell Solar Materials except DYI. Chlorobenzene (CB, 99%), isopropanol (IPA, 99.9%), anhydrous dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, 99.8%), and N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.8%) were purchased from Acros Organics.

Cyanoguanidinium diiodide (DYI) synthesis: Cyanoguanidine iodide salt was synthesized through inverse temperature crystallization of dicyandiamide using hydroiodic acid and hypophosphorous acid (v/v= 10:1) (57%, TCI Chemicals and 50%, Acros chemicals). The obtained precipitate was washed with diethyl ether (Acros Organics) and subjected to multiple recrystallization steps using absolute ethanol. This washing and recrystallization process was repeated several times to ensure purity using the rotavapor. Finally, the resulting crystals were dried under a vacuum for 10 hours and stored in an argon glovebox (Figure S12a).

Device Fabrication: The ITO-coated glasses were sequentially cleaned using ultrasonication with Hellmanex II solution (2 vol% in DI water), followed by deionized water, acetone, ethanol, and isopropanol respectively with 20 minutes for each step. The cleaned substrates were dried with compressed air. Subsequently, the dried substrates were treated with UV–ozone for 30 minutes before device fabrication. SnO_2 colloidal solution ($\text{SnO}_2:\text{H}_2\text{O} = 4:1$ (v/v)) was spin-coated on the ITO substrate with 2 steps at 500 rpm for 5s and 3000 rpm for 30s, followed by annealing at 140°C for 30 min. The obtained films were transferred to the glove box (H_2O level: <0.1 ppm and O_2 level: <1 ppm), then annealed again at 140°C for 10 min, the triple-cation perovskite $\text{Cs}_{0.05}\text{FA}_{0.9}\text{MA}_{0.05}\text{PbI}_3$ were deposited in a single step. The perovskite precursor solution at 1.3M in DMF and DMSO (v/v = 4/1), was spin-coated at 1000 rpm for 10s followed by 6000 rpm for 30s, 125 μL of chlorobenzene was used as antisolvent in the last 10s. The as-deposited films were annealed at 100°C for 1h and then at 150°C for 10

min. for the surface passivation PEAI, ImI, and DYI, 50 μL from each solution (2 mg/ml in IPA) were spin-coated dynamically on top of the perovskite at 4000 rpm for 30s. The hole transport material (HTM) was prepared by dissolving 72.3 mg of Spiro-OMeTAD in chlorobenzene, doped by 17.6 μL of LiTFSI (520 mg/ml in Acetonitrile) and 28.5 μL of t-BP. Next, 35 μL of the HTM solution was dropped on the substrate and spin-coated at 4000 rpm for 30 seconds. Finally, an Ag electrode (100 nm) was thermally evaporated under a pressure of 4×10^{-6} Torr.

Thin Film Characterisation: The thin film of perovskite with different passivators was characterized by spectroscopic techniques such as UV-vis, FT-IR, $^1\text{H-NMR}$, PL, SEM, and XRD. The absorption spectra and steady-state photoluminescence (PL) measurements were obtained using a UV-vis spectrophotometer (Varian Cary 60 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer) and a fluorescence spectrophotometer (PerkinElmer 55 Instrument). Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) spectra were measured using a Jasco FT-IR-6100 spectrometer in Attenuated Total Reflectance mode (ATR-FTIR). The spectra were recorded over wavelengths ranging from 450 to 4000 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 1 cm^{-1} . $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectra were obtained with a Varian Mercury 400 MHz spectrometer in d_6 -(DMSO) solvent. The surface and cross-sectional images were obtained using a Hitachi S-4800 scanning electron microscope (SEM), respectively. X-ray diffractograms were recorded using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with Bragg-Brentano geometry and a Cu $K\alpha$ X-ray tube with a wavelength (λ) of 1.5406 Å. The Atomic force microscope (AFM) images were captured using a Park Systems NX10 equipped with a non-contact silicon cantilever.

Device Characterisation: The photovoltaic characteristics were assessed under irradiation of 1000 W m^{-2} (AM1.5, 1 sun) using a 3A Oriel solar simulator from Newport. The device's active area was maintained at 0.09 cm^2 through the use of a black metal mask. Incident Photon-to-Current Efficiency (IPCE) spectra were recorded with a 150 W Xenon lamp connected to a Bentham PVE300 motorized 1/4 m monochromator. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were conducted using a Palmsens4 potentiostat over a frequency range of 1-MHz to 1-Hz with a 15 mV perturbation.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or the author.

Author Contributions

MG performed the experiments, SK guided the project and supported electro-optical characterization, and SA conceptualized and directed the project.

Acknowledgements

This work received funding from the European Union H2020 Programme under a European Research Council Consolidator grant [MOLEMAT, 726360]. Support from the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (PID2019-111774RB-100/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and INTERACTION (PID2021-129085OB-I00)) is acknowledged.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data supporting the findings are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Received: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

Revised: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

Published online: ((will be filled in by the editorial staff))

References

- [1] Y. Yang, C. Liu, Y. Ding, B. Ding, J. Xu, A. Liu, J. Yu, L. Grater, H. Zhu, S. S. Hadke, V. K. Sangwan, A. S. R. Bati, X. Hu, J. Li, S. M. Park, M. C. Hersam, B. Chen, M. Khaja Nazeeruddin, M. G. Kanatzidis, E. H. Sargent, *Nat. Energy* **2024**, 9, 316–323.
- [2] S. M. Park, M. Wei, N. Lempesis, W. Yu, T. Hossain, L. Agosta, V. Carnevali, H. R. Atapattu, P. Serles, F. T. Eickemeyer, H. Shin, M. Vafaie, D. Choi, K. Darabi, E. Dae Jung, Y. Yang, D. Bin Kim, S. M. Zakeeruddin, B. Chen, A. Amassian, T. Filleter, M. G. Kanatzidis, K. R. Graham, L. Xiao, U. Rothlisberger, M. Grätzel, E. H. Sargent, *Nature* **2023**, 624, 289-294.
- [3] S. Zhang, F. Ye, X. Wang, R. Chen, H. Zhang, L. Zhan, X. Jiang, Y. Li, X. Ji, S. Liu, M. Yu, F. Yu, Y. Zhang, R. Wu, Z. Liu, Z. Ning, D. Neher, L. Han, Y. Lin, H. Tian, W. Chen, M. Stollerfoht, L. Zhang, W.-H. Zhu, Y. Wu, *Science* **2023**, 380, 404–409.
- [4] J. Park, J. Kim, H.-S. Yun, M. J. Paik, E. Noh, H. J. Mun, M. G. Kim, J. Shin, Sang, I. Seok, *Nature* **2023**, 616, 724-730.
- [5] D. Luo, R. Su, W. Zhang, Q. Gong, R. Zhu, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **2020**, 5, 44–60.

- [6] J. Diekmann, P. Caprioglio, M. H. Futscher, V. M. Le Corre, S. Reichert, F. Jaiser, M. Arvind, L. P. Toro, E. Gutierrez-Partida, F. Peña-Camargo, C. Deibel, B. Ehrler, T. Unold, T. Kirchartz, D. Neher, M. Stollerfoht, *Solar RRL* **2021**, 5, 2100219.
- [7] W. Peng, K. Mao, F. Cai, H. Meng, Z. Zhu, T. Li, S. Yuan, Z. Xu, X. Feng, J. Xu, M. D. McGehee, J. Xu, *Science* **2023**, 379, 638–690.
- [8] X. Liu, Y. Cheng, B. Tang, Z. G. Yu, M. Li, F. Lin, S. Zhang, Y. W. Zhang, J. Ouyang, H. Gong, *Nano Energy* **2020**, 71, 104556.
- [9] S. Fu, J. Le, X. Guo, N. Sun, W. Zhang, W. Song, J. Fang, S. Fu, J. Le, N. Sun, W. Song, J. Fang, X. Guo, W. Zhang, *Advanced Materials* **2022**, 34, 2205066.
- [10] M. M. Byranvand, M. Saliba, *Solar RRL* **2021**, 5, 2100295.
- [11] M. Jeong, I. Woo Choi, E. Min Go, Y. Cho, M. Kim, B. Lee, S. Jeong, Y. Jo, H. Won Choi, J. Lee, J.-H. Bae, S. Kyu Kwak, D. Suk Kim, C. Yang, *Science* **2020**, 369, 1615–1620.
- [12] Z. Wu, E. Bi, L. K. Ono, D. Li, O. M. Bakr, Y. Yan, Y. Qi, *Nano Energy* **2023**, 10873; W. Han, X. Liu, X. Zhang, Y. Ding, Y. Guo, *Org. Electron.* **2021**, 96, 106226.
- [13] C. Zhang, H. Li, C. Gong, Q. Zhuang, J. Chen, Z. Zang, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2023**, 16, 3825; Q. Wen, C. Duan, F. Zou, D. Luo, J. Li, Z. Liu, J. Wang, K. Yan, *Chem. Eng. J.* **2023**, 452, 139697.
- [14] X. Pu, Q. Cao, X. He, J. Su, W. Wang, X. Zhang, D. Wang, Y. Zhang, J. Yang, T. Wang, H. Chen, L. Jiang, Y. Yan, X. Chen, X. Li, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2024**, 14, 2303972.
- [15] Z. Zhang, ad Lu Qiao, K. Meng, R. Long, G. Chen, P. Gao, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2023**, 52, 163.
- [16] M. Pegu, S. Kazim, T. Buffeteau, D. M. Bassani, S. Ahmad, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2021**, 13, 48219–48227.
- [17] Q. Jiang, Y. Zhao, X. Zhang, X. Yang, Y. Chen, Z. Chu, Q. Ye, X. Li, Z. Yin, J. You, *Nat. Photonics*, **2019**, 13, 460–466.
- [18] H. Zhang, L. Pfeifer, S. M. Zakeeruddin, J. Chu, M. Grätzel. *Nat. Rev. Chem.* **2023**, 7, 632–652.
- [19] C. Ma, M.-C. Kang, S.-H. Lee, Y. Zhang, D.-H. Kang, W. Yang, S.-W. Kim, J. Kwon, C.-W. Yang, Y. Yang, N.-G. Park, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2023**, 145, 24349–24357.
- [20] S. Svanströ, T. J. Jacobsson, G. Boschloo, E. M. J. Johansson, H. Rensmo, U. B. Cappel, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2020**, 12, 7221.
- [21] H. Li, Z. Yan, M. Li, X. Wen, S. Deng, S. Liu, W. C. H. Choy, L. Li, M. Y. Li, H. Lu, *Chem. Eng. J.* **2023**, 458, 141405.
- [22] Z. Liu, Z. Su, B. Yu, Y. Sun, J. Zhang, H. Yu, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces.* **2024**, 16, 31218–31227.

- [23] J. Jeong, M. Kim, J. Seo, H. Lu, P. Ahlawat, A. Mishra, Y. Yang, M. A. Hope, F. T. Eickemeyer, M. Kim, Y. Jin Yoon, I. W. Choi, B. P. Darwich, S. J. Choi, Y. Jo, J. H. Lee, B. Walker, S. M. Zakeeruddin, L. Emsley, U. Rothlisberger, A. Hagfeldt, D. S. Kim, M. Grätzel, J. Y. Kim, *Nature*. **2021**, 592, 381.
- [24] K. M. Muhammed Salim, T. Ming Koh, D. Bahulayan, P. C. Harikesh, N. Fadilah Jamaludin, B. Febriansyah, A. Bruno, S. Mhaisalkar, N. Mathews, N. Link, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2018**, 3, 1068–1076.
- [25] T. P. Baumeler, E. A. Alharbi, G. Kakavelakis, G. C. Fish, M. T. Aldosari, M. S. Albishi, L. Pfeifer, B. I. Carlsen, J.-H. Yum, A. S. Alharbi, M. D. Mensi, J. Gao, F. T. Eickemeyer, K. Sivula, J.-E. Moser, S. M. Zakeeruddin, M. Grätzel, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2023**, 8, 2456–2462.
- [26] H. Zhang, W. Xiang, X. Zuo, X. Gu, S. Zhang, Y. Du, Z. Wang, Y. Liu, H. Wu, P. Wang, Q. Cui, H. Su, Q. Tian, S. Liu, *Angew. Chem.* **2023**, 135, e202216634.
- [27] W. Cai, Y. Wang, W. Li, Y. Yin, J. Liu, W. Cai, S. Wang, J. Guo, S. Chang, S. Li, X. Wang, Y. Shi, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2024**, 2304521.
- [28] Y. Cai, J. Cui, M. Chen, M. Zhang, Y. Han, F. Qian, H. Zhao, S. Yang, Z. Yang, H. Bian, T. Wang, K. Guo, M. Cai, S. Dai, Z. Liu, S. Liu, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2021**, 31, 2005776.
- [29] Y. Wu, Q. Liang, H. Zhu, X. Dai, B.-B. Yu, Y. Hu, M. Chen, L.-B. Huang, S. M. Zakeeruddin, Z. Shen, J. Wang, M. Grätzel, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2023**, 33, 2302404.
- [30] A. Ghaderian, N. H. Hemasiri, S. Ahmad, S. Kazim, *Energy Technol.* **2023**, 11, 2200211.
- [31] H. Beng Lee, M.-K. Jeon, N. Kumar, B. Tyagi, J.-W. Kang, H. B. Lee, M. Jeon, N. Kumar, B. Tyagi, J. Kang, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2019**, 29, 1903213.
- [32] Y. Kong, W. Shen, H. Cai, W. Dong, C. Bai, J. Zhao, F. Huang, Y.-B. Cheng, J. Zhong, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2023**, 33, 2300932.
- [33] V. M. Le Corre, E. A. Duijnste, O. El Tambouli, J. M. Ball, H. J. Snaith, J. Lim, L. Jan, A. Koster, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2021**, 6, 1087–1094.
- [34] J. Xu, H. Chen, L. Grater, C. Liu, Y. Yang, S. Teale, A. Maxwell, S. Mahesh, H. Wan, Y. Chang, B. Chen, B. Rehl, S. M. Park, M. G. Kanatzidis, E. H. Sargent, *Nat. Mater.* **2023**, 22, 1507–1514.
- [35] H. Sun, S. Wang, S. Qi, P. Wang, R. Li, B. Shi, Q. Zhang, Q. Huang, S. Xu, Y. Zhao, X. Zhang, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2023**, 33, 2213913.
- [36] J. Liang, X. Hu, C. Wang, C. Liang, C. Chen, M. Xiao, J. Li, C. Tao, G. Xing, R. Yu, W. Ke, G. Fang, *Joule*. **2022**, 6, 816–833.
- [37] J.-H. Kim, D.-H. Kang, D.-N. Lee, N.-G. Park, *J. Mater. Chem. A*. **2023**, 11, 15014–15021.

- [38] Y. Meng, J. Zhang, C. Liu, K. Zheng, L. Xie, S. Bu, B. Han, R. Cao, X. Yin, C. Liu, Z. Ge, *Adv. Funct. Mater.*, **2022**, 33, 2210600.
- [39] M. Casareto, N. Rolston, 2022, *Commun. Mater.* **2024**, 5, 74.